

Polarographic Studies on Electrode Kinetics of Zirconium

J. N. GAUR, D. S. JAIN and ASHOK MAHESHWARI

Chemistry Department, Rajasthan University, Jaipur-4

Manuscript Received 5 July 1974; revised 16 October 1974; accepted 1 March 1975

The reduction of zirconium at the dropping mercury electrode in sodium perchlorate, tetramethyl ammonium bromide and tetra-ethyl ammonium iodide solutions has been studied. The reduction is diffusion-controlled but the process is not reversible. The kinetic parameters have been calculated by Koutecky method and also by Meites and Israel treatment for irreversible reductions. The effect of temperature on the kinetic parameters have been investigated. As the temperature increases, the reduction becomes more reversible.

FROM the survey of literature it was found that very little attention has been paid so far towards the reduction of zirconium at dropping mercury electrode because of high negative half-wave potential which is preceded by hydrogen discharge. The reduction of zirconium in aqueous medium has been investigated by number of workers¹⁻⁴. Polarography of zirconium in chloride, perchlorate and nitrate as indifferent electrolytes has been studied by Gaur and Goswami⁵. The reduction of zirconium in dimethyl sulfoxide and aqueous dimethyl sulfoxide has been investigated by Sancho and Pujante⁶, whereas Gutmann and Schober has carried out the studies in anhydrous ethylenediamine⁷ and dimethyl sulfoxide⁸. In methyl alcohol, the investigations were performed by Pentani and Desideri⁹ and Zakharov and Stromberg¹⁰.

However, the data on electrode kinetics are very few. The present paper deals with the reduction of zirconium in sodium perchlorate, tetramethyl ammonium bromide and tetraethyl ammonium iodide at dropping mercury electrode. The electrode kinetics has been studied by Koutecky¹¹ method and also by Meites and Israel treatment¹² for irreversible reduction and the mechanism has been explained.

Experimental

A manual polarographic set up was used to measure the current-voltage curves. The d.m.e. had the following characteristic $m=1.92$ mg/sec. and $t=4.2$ sec. (at $-1.0V$ vs S. C. E. in $1M$ $NaClO_4$). The reductions were carried out in a H-type cell with an agar-agar plug saturated with sodium chloride. The dissolved oxygen was removed by bubbling purified N_2 gas through the solutions for 25-30 min. All the measurements were done at 30° and 40° which was maintained with a Haake type Ultrathermostat. Stock solution of zirconium was prepared by dissolving reagent grade zirconium oxychloride in doubly distilled water. Polarographically pure sodium perchlorate, tetramethyl ammonium bromide and tetra ethyl ammonium iodide were used as base electrolytes. Solutions containing $1mM$ of zirconium and $.1M$ of base electrolytes were prepared and polarographed after deaeration. The pH of the each solution was measured and was found to $3.4 \pm .1$.

Results and Discussion

A single well developed reduction wave appeared in each case. The plots i_d (i_d = wave height) vs \sqrt{h} (h =

effective height of mercury column) were linear and passes through origin for all the solutions. This indicate that reductions are diffusion controlled. The plots of

$\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ is linear in all the cases. The values

of the slopes show that the reductions are irreversible. The electrode reaction for reduction of zirconyl ions at dropping mercury electrode takes place according to the following mechanism,

which involves two electrons. The polarographic data obtained with $1mM$ zirconium in various supporting electrolytes are given in Table 1. The kinetic parameters have been determined by Koutecky¹¹ method as discussed below :

The mathematical solution for an electrode reaction at d.m.e. controlled by kinetics of electron transfer is given by

$$\frac{i}{i_d} = F(X) - \xi H_c(X) = F'(X) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } X = \left(\frac{12}{7}\right)^{1/2} K_{th} \frac{t^{1/2}}{D_0^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

t is drop time,
 D_0 is diffusion coefficient,
 K_{th} is potential dependent heterogenous rate constant described by

$$K_{th} = K_{th}^0 \exp. \frac{nF(E+0.2412)}{RT} \quad (3)$$

$$\xi = 50.4 D_0^{1/2} m^{-1/8} t^{1/8}$$

where E is referred to S.C.E, i and i_d are current at end of the drop life at potential E and on plateau of the wave respectively.

From the value of $\frac{i}{i_d}$ at various selected potentials

the corresponding functions 'X' may be obtained from the original table of Koutecky. Plotting of $\log X$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ then gives values of K_{th}^0 and α_n . For this purpose it is convenient to combine preceding equation with

$$\log_{10}(X) = \log_{10} \left(\frac{12}{7}\right)^{1/2} \frac{K_{th}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_0^{1/2}} - \frac{\alpha nF(E+0.2412)}{2.303RT} \quad (4)$$

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF ZIRCONIUM (1MM) IN DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES (0.1M)

Supporting electrolyte (0.1M)	Temp. °C	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCF)	i_d (μ A)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^8$ (cm ² /sec)	αn	K_{fh}^0 Koutecky's method	K_{fh}^0 Meites and Israel method
Sodium perchlorate	30	1.515	4.3	122	1.93	0.44	1.0×10^{-14}	3.11×10^{-14}
Tetramethyl ammonium bromide	30	1.449	3.3	98	1.48	0.55	7.94×10^{-15}	9.93×10^{-16}
Tetraethyl ammonium iodide	30	1.445	3.4	83.5	1.53	0.65	1.99×10^{-16}	2.69×10^{-16}
Sodium perchlorate	40	1.487	4.5	113	2.02	0.48	1.95×10^{-14}	—
Tetramethyl ammonium bromide	40	1.422	3.65	87	1.64	0.62	1.0×10^{-14}	—
Tetraethyl ammonium iodide	40	1.432	3.8	85	1.71	0.63	1.14×10^{-15}	—

Now plot of $\log X$ vs $E(N. H. E.)$ shall be linear. Thus the value of K_{fh}^0 is obtained while the value of αn is obtained from slope of plot (Fig. 1).

Meites and Israel^{1,2} have simplified the calculations of K_{fh}^0 by taking advantage that for value of $\frac{i}{i_d}$ between 0.1 to 0.95 Koutecky's values for X and $\frac{i}{i_d}$ corresponds to a linear relationship between $\log X$ and $\frac{i}{i_d - i}$.

Thus at 25° the equation for a totally irreversible wave becomes.

$$E_{d.e.} + 0.2412 = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (5)$$

which may be again written as

$$E_{d.e.} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \log \frac{i}{i_d - i} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{with } E_{1/2} = -0.2412 + \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{fh}^0 t^{1/2}}{D_o^{1/2}} \quad (7)$$

$E_{d.e.}$ and $E_{1/2}$ are referred to S.C.E.

Thus the value of αn was obtained from slope $-\frac{0.0542}{\alpha n}$ of straight line of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$. The

intercept of the same plot gave the value of $E_{1/2}$ which was used to calculate K_{fh}^0 after having the value of $D_o^{1/2}$ from the Ilkovic equation. The values of K_{fh}^0 are calculated for different supporting electrolytes and

recorded in Table 1. Results obtained by Meites and Israel method are slightly different than those obtained by Koutecky method. As the Meites and Israel method is mathematical in comparison to Koutecky's method which is graphical one, it is obvious that results obtained by Meites and Israel method are more correct than those obtained with Koutecky method. The value of K_{fh}^0 at 40° are greater than 30° suggesting that the reduction proceed much faster or the irreversibility decreases with increase of temperature.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to the University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for financial support.

References

1. R. P. GRAHAM, E. VAN DALM and H. M. C. UPRON, *Canad J. Chem.*, (1952), 30, 1069.
2. I. A. KORSHUNOV and N. L. MALYUGINA, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, (1959) 4, 1077.
3. J. STRADIUS and L. LIEPINA, *Chem. Abs.*, (1960), 110f.
4. D. COZZI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 6741h.
5. N. K. GOSWAMI and J. N. GAUR., *Indian J. Chem.* 1961, 5, 421.
6. J. SANCHO and A. PUJANTE., *An. Quim.* 1968, 64, 9-4.
7. V. GUTMANN and G. SCHOBER., *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1957, 88, 206.
8. V. GUTMANN and G. SCHOBER., *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1959, 171, 339.
9. P. G. DISIDERI, F. PENTANI and D. A. ESTRATOO., *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 5, 16223d.
10. M. S. ZAKHAROV and A. G. STROMBERG., *Anal. Abs.*, 2184, 1965, 12.
11. J. KOUTECKY., *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953; 18, 579; 1956, 21, 836.
12. L. MEITES and Y. ISRAEL., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4903.